

Neil Chakraborti, Jon Garland, *Hate Crime – Impact, Causes & Responses*, Second Edition (Sage Publications: 2015), Pages: 208, Price: \$24.99.

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Hate crime refers to those crimes in society that have been stimulated by prejudice for a certain social group, ethnicity, religion, language or gender identity, etc. Hate crime is now prevalent across the world and has a remarkable impact not only on the victim but on the entire community. The book, *Hate Crime – Impact, Causes & Responses*, brings to the notice of readers not only the nature and extent but also the impact and disputes with the policy making. This book also covers the new realm of hate crimes like cyber bullying and online hate.

Neil Chakraborti is Professor of Criminology at the University of Leicester and an Adjunct Professor at the University of Ontario Institute of Technology. He has conducted research in various fields including victimisation, crime and policing. Jon Garland has been a Reader at the University of Surrey's Department of Sociology since January 2013; his main areas of research are in the fields of hate crime, rural racism, community and identity, policing and victimisation.

The book explores various dimensions of hate crimes. The author begins by looking at the various features of hate crime like marginalisation, victimisation and difference in the light of conceptual understanding. It also talks about the laws ratified by the UK to protect its citizens.

The authors have observed that the most common form of hate crimes that people face are racist hate crimes. This crime is aroused by an individual's ethnic identity. "Low levels" of racist's harassment like blocking the driveways, throwing eggs, etc, have become part and parcel of the targetted ethnic communities. The book sheds light upon the emergence of racist hate crime in UK by examining the scope of and legal framework that has been used to deal with the victims of such hate crimes.

Over the years we have seen how a particular religion has been blamed and scrutinised for terrorism happening across the globe. Such scrutinisations have led to target communities on the basis of their religious beliefs which then are manifested into secular constructions of cultural and national identity. The book

also primarily focusses upon *Islamophobia* (*prejudice against Islam or Muslims*) & *Antisemitism* (*prejudice against Jews*). Thus, the laws that have been formed put religious communities on the same level as minority ethnic communities in terms of guiding their identities and rights in the eyes of the law.

Homophobia, a very serious and contemporary issue, is the fear or hatred of homosexuals and homosexuality. The book article encompasses the nature, extent and effects of the homophobic hate crime. A major reason behind the rise of this crime is the relationship between the police and gay community which has damaged the trust and the confidence between the two parties. Low level of harassment is common for these communities and the assaults targeted towards such groups have been of extreme nature than those of other crimes.

Gender is not something that is biological but is rather a socially raised phenomenon that is subjected to an individual. Transphobic hate crimes are more frequent and have a significant impact on the victims as compared to other hate crimes. Transphobic hate crimes have come up due to fear/hatred against the transgenders or trans-sexuals. The book also tries to understand the grounds of the perpetrator's action.

Disabilist hate crimes have recently caught attention from the academics as well as the criminal justice system. This hate crime occurs because the perpetrator believes that the disabled people are inferior to others. The issue of 'cuckooing' is also discussed in the chapter.

The book explores the nature and extent of crimes against domestic violence, elder abuse attacks upon sex workers and the homeless.

The book also investigates the various types of hate crime offenders along with their motivation and relationship with the victim. It has been frequently seen that hate crimes are being enacted for the excitement and delight involved rather than the hatred towards a particular group or individual. Generally, males belonging to deprived backgrounds have been major perpetrators of hate crimes.

A reason behind the growing number of cases for hate crimes is the troubled relationship between the police and the minority communities. This relationship affects the response of the police towards a hate crime. The chapter examines few theoretical, cultural and operational complexities that have distorted the policing of hate crimes.

Towards the end, the book reassesses the various concepts of hate crimes that have been discussed in the previous chapters along with future directions for future research, policy and practice.

Hate crimes are a relevant issue across the globe, especially so in India, where there is a lot of diversity in terms of culture, religion and socio-economic status. This book helps us understand the concept of hate crimes and their impact on the victims as well as the communities.